

Mesoporous silica nanoparticles as redox-responsive drug delivery system

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In the last years, nanomaterials, such as mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs), have become relevant in biomedicine due to their unique properties, particular size, huge specific surface and the possibility of functionalization of their surface. This functionalization allows to create devices which can act as smart drug delivery vehicles in cancer therapy, avoiding premature liberation of drugs prior to reach the tumor and cancer cells. In this research work we propose a novel redox-responsive drug delivery system based on MSNs with a disulfide cross-linked dendrimeric network grafted to their external surface, acting as coating and capping agent. A large group of advanced techniques has been employed for the complete characterization of the organo-inorganic hybrid nanoparticles, and the redox-responsive drug delivery behaviour of the nanosystem has been assayed by means of a release test under low redox potential simulated conditions.

1 Introduction

The design and development of new materials in cancer therapy has become one of principal targets in medicine so great efforts are being made to find new strategies to treat cancer, less invasive and without side effects for patients. Even more, enormous work is being done by researches to develop new materials able to diagnose and treat cancer concurrently, a new type of clinical practice which is called theragnosis, a powerful tool in biomedicine to defeat cancer.¹

Nanotechnology plays a crucial role in the seeking of new materials for cancer therapy. Enhanced Permeation and Retention (EPR) effect occurs in solid tumors, which quickly grew a vascular system to feed itself and to take out its metabolic residues.² The main consequence of this fast growth, is a ragged vascular construction with tiny perforations (100-300 nm). Here is where nanotechnology can help by developing nanometric materials able to pass from systemic circulation to the solid tumor through these nanometric fenestrations and, once within the tumor, these nanomaterials will be withheld, due to the poor lymphatic drainage of the tumors, being able to do their required function.³

Another step forward in cancer therapy is the use of stimulus-responsive nanomaterials for controlled drug delivery, allowing to overcome one of the challenges above mentioned, side effects. Traditional chemotherapy employees highly cytotoxic drugs that kills tumoral cells but, although in less proportion, healthy cells are prone to death as well. Smart drug delivery systems not only allow to transport cytotoxic drugs, but also to deliver them in specific tissues in response to an external or internal stimulus, avoiding their premature release in healthy tissues.⁴

Among the different nanomaterials available for these purposes, here we focus on MCM-41 type MSNs, which, since the discovery of M41S mesoporous silica materials in 1992 by Mobil's researchers,⁵ have attracted the attention of many fields in science, far away from their first purposes as catalysis molecular sieves. For biomedicine applications, it was in 2001 when for the first time the use of MCM-41 mesoporous silica material as drug delivery system was reported, showing enhanced drug adsorption and release kinetics.⁶ From that date, MCM-41 type MSNs have

emerged as promising smart drug delivery systems due to their unique features, such as their hexagonal ordered array of cylindrical mesopores (2-50 nm) with a volumen of *ca.* 1 cm³/g which allows to host large and quantified amounts of a huge range of drugs and biomolecules, large surface area (*ca.* 1000 m²/g) available for adsorption of drugs, -SiOH rich surface ready for any required functionalization, and maybe which could be the most important feature in biomedicine, biocompatibility.⁷ A wide variety of synthetic strategies for tailoring these features, as well as to choose their size from 20 nm up to 700 nm in monodispersed spheres are available.^{8,9}

To date, a large variety of MSNs based stimulus-responsive drug delivery systems have been reported. Different types of stimuli can be exploit to trigger a locked system. These stimuli can be external (radiation with light, application of magnetic/electric fields, variations in temperature, application of ultrasonic waves), or specific for a type of tissue (variations in pH, presence of different enzymes/molecules, different redox conditions).¹⁰ Particularly for redox-responsive systems with disulfide bridges, the stimulus is originated by the lower reduction potential conditions at cytoplasm in tumoral cells, where the existence of glutathione (GSH) molecules, which present -SH groups in its structure, acts as a reducing agent able to break disulfide bridges.¹¹

Many different strategies have been exploited in order to cap MSNs for redox triggering, such as the use of reductively sheddable polymer shell as sealing agent,¹² capping by disulfide-bonded collagen,¹³ using snap-top systems employing MSNs functionalized with rotaxanes incorporating disulfide bridges in their stalks,¹⁴ and many more. Herein, we propose the use of a redox-sensitive cross-linked dendrimeric network as coating and capping agent for the MSNs mesopores. Dendrimers are tree-like highly branched macromolecules that possess unique three-dimensional architectures. Their main features include monodisperse polymeric constitution, nanometer dimensions and the presence of a large number of functionalities on the surface.¹⁵ Focusing on the biomedical applications of polyamine dendrimers,¹⁶ such as the ones employed in this work, one of their most remarkable uses is as non-viral vehicles in gene transfection therapies.¹⁷ Thus, the smart drug-delivery system we introduce here is the starting point of a multifunctional material not only for drug delivery, but also for gene transfection if required.

In this work we develop a novel redox-responsive drug delivery system, which lies in MCM-41 type spherical MSNs bearing third generation poly(propyleneimine) (3G-PPI) den-

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Scheme 1 A schematic representation of the steps involved in the redox-responsive drug delivery system.

drimers covalently grafted onto the external surface of the MSNs. Subsequently, these dendrimers are cross-linked through *N,N'*-cystamine bisacrylamide (CBA), a disulfide-bridged molecule which breaks in two parts under low redox potential conditions, enabling the redox-responsive properties of the system. The working principle of the system is straight forward as shown in Scheme 1: after the dendrimers are grafted onto the MSNs, the dye molecule/drug is loaded into the MSNs pores and subsequently CBA cross-linker is added, bunching up the dendrimers each other, leading to a protective fence at the outlet of the pores and hindering the drug to scape. Eventually, under a simulated reductive environment, the disulfide bridge of CBA is broken apart, and therefore the drug is free to diffuse from the mesopores.

2 Experimental section

2.1 Chemicals and methods

The reaction for the synthesis of the dendrimeric precursor and its covalent bond to the MSNs surface, as well as the dendrimeric coating cross-linking reaction, were performed under nitrogen protective atmosphere using standard Schlenk techniques. Dichloromethane (CH_2Cl_2) was dried by typical procedures over phosphorus (V) oxide, distilled and degassed immediately prior to use. All reagent-grade chemical employed were purchased from the following suppliers and used without further purification unless otherwise noted: tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), *N,N*-Diisopropylethylamine (Hünig's base), acryloyl chloride and DL-dithiothreitol (DTT) from Sigma-Aldrich, fluorescein free acid (FFA), hexamethylenediamine and cystamine dihydrochloride from Fluka Analytical, 3-(triethoxysilyl)propyl isocyanate from ABCR GmbH & Co., and the 3G-PPI dendrimers [$\text{G}_3(\text{NH}_2)_{16}$] from SyMO-Chem. All other chemicals [ethanol (EtOH), ammonium nitrate (NH_4NO_3), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), etc] were of the best quality commercially available and used as received.

Milli-Q water (18.2 M Ω) was prepared using a Milli-Q Synthesis System (Millipore, US). N_2 sorption measurements were obtained by using a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 analyzer at -196°C . Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images were acquired using a JEOL 6535 microscope at 15 kV. Powder Low-Angle X-Ray Diffraction (LA XRD) patterns were acquired on PANalytical X-Pert PRO high-resolution diffractometer. Thermo Gravimetric Analysis (TGA) and Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA) studies were performed in air between 30 and 800°C with a flow rate of 100 mL/min and a heating rate of $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ using a Perkin Elmer Pyris Diamon thermobalance. Elemental Analysis (EA) studies were performed in a LECO CHNS 932 system. Fluores-

cence spectroscopy measurements were carried out in a Synergy 4 Biotek fluorimeter set at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 490\text{ nm}$ and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 514\text{ nm}$. ^1H and ^{13}C Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectra were collected from a Bruker AV 250 MHz equipment, and ^1H and ^{13}C High Resolution Magic Angle Spinning (HR MAS) NMR spectra from a Bruker AMX 500 MHz system. Solid state ^{13}C , ^{29}Si MAS NMR and ^{29}Si cross-polarization (CP) MAS NMR spectra were measured in a Bruker Avance AV-400WB spectrometer equipped with a solid state probe using a 4 mm zirconia rotor. Fourier Transformed InfraRed (FT-IR) spectra were collected in a Thermo Nicolet Nexus spectrometer equipped with a *Golden-gate* Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR) device. Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) and zeta-potential (ξ) measurements were carried out in a Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Instruments) equipped with a 633 nm red laser. ElectroSpray Ionization Mass Spectrometry (ESI MS) analyses were conducted on a ESQUIRE HCT-Ultra connected to a HPLC system with ESI interface.

2.2 Synthesis of cross-linking agents

Redox-sensitive cross-linker CBA was synthesized using a procedure similar to the previously described in literature (Scheme 2).¹⁸ Briefly, cystamine dihydrochloride (3.078 g, 0.013 mol) was dissolved in water (15 mL) and placed in a three necks flask. After the solution was cooled to $0\text{--}5^\circ\text{C}$, a solution of acryloyl chloride (2.24 mL, 0.027 mol) in CH_2Cl_2 (5 mL) and an aqueous NaOH solution (5 mL, 2 M) were added simultaneously from two different dropping funnels. After the addition was completed, the reaction mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature (RT) under darkness, and a white precipitate appeared. Subsequently, the solid was filtrated and extensively washed with water. The raw product was further purified by crystallization using acetonitrile/heptane (50% v/v). Finally, the CBA was vacuum dried overnight at RT. ^1H NMR studies together with EA and ESI MS probed the high purity of the final product and the lack of polymerization or disulfide cleavage. δ_{H} (250 MHz; CDCl_3) 6.78 (2H, br, NH), 6.19 (4H, m, $\text{CHH}=\text{CHCO}$), 5.57 (2H, d, $\text{CHH}=\text{CHCO}$), 3.56 (4H, q, NHCH_2), 2.79 (4H, t, CH_2S). EA calculated for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$: C, 46.13; H, 6.19; N, 10.76; O, 12.29; S, 24.63. Found: C, 46.05; H, 6.16; N, 10.75; S, 24.44. ESI MS (*m/z*, %):

Scheme 2 CBA and HBA synthetic procedure.

261.1 (3.52) $[M + H]^+$, 283.0 (100) $[M + Na]^+$, 284.0 (8.57) $[M_0 + Na^+ + H]^2+$, 285.0 (4.81) $[M_0 + Na^+ + 2H]^3+$, 543.1 (3.01) $[2M_0 + Na]^+$.

Control cross-linker 1,6-hexamethylenediacrylamide (HBA) was prepared in a similar way to CBA (Scheme 2). Highly hygroscopic hexamethylenediamine (1.59 g, 0.013 mol) weighed under inert atmosphere, was dissolved in 15 mL of water at 0–5 °C, and the next steps followed the same procedure than the described for CBA. Finally, sharp white needle-shape crystals were obtained and purity was assessed by 1H NMR studies, together with EA. δ_H (250 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 6.17 (4H, m, $CHH=CHCO$), 5.90 (2H, br, NH), 5.65 (2H, d, $CHH=CHCO$), 3.32 (4H, q, $NHCH_2$), 1.54 (8H, m, $NHCH_2CH_2$). EA calculated for $C_{12}H_{20}N_2O_2$: C, 64.26; H, 8.99; N, 12.49; O, 14.27. EA found for CBA C, 64.06 H, 8.69; N, 12.55.

2.3 Dendrimer silylation

Following the procedure described by González *et al.*,¹⁹ a solution of 3-isocyanatopropyltriethoxysilane (73 μ L, 0.3 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (150 mL) was added dropwise to a vigorous stirred solution of 3G-PPI dendrimers in dry CH_2Cl_2 (160 mL), under inert atmosphere. The reaction mixture was stirred overnight at RT for its immediate use. The proper progress of reaction was controlled by FTIR and 1H NMR spectroscopies.

2.4 Preparation of redox-responsive MSNs

MSNs were prepared by a sol-gel approach, as previously reported in the literature.²⁰ A solution of CTAB (1 g, 0.003 mol) of water (480 mL) with 3.5 mL of a NaOH 2M was heated to 80 °C under stable stirring. Subsequently, 5 mL of TEOS were added dropwise with assistance of a syringe pump at a constant rate of 0.25 mL/min. The mixture was allowed to stir for 2 h at 80 °C and then cooled to RT. The nanoparticles were extensively washed with water and ethanol using centrifugation. Finally, the particles were vacuum dried overnight at 40 °C, giving rise to a white solid dust. In order to remove the surfactant template from the mesopores, the as-synthesized MSNs were stirred in an extracting solution of NH_4NO_3 (10 g/L) in EtOH/ H_2O (95:5, v/v), in a ratio of 3 g of MSNs per litre of extracting solution, during 6 hours at 65 °C. The surfactant-free MSNs were thoroughly washed with EtOH. The extracting process was repeated a second time and the surfactant-free MSNs were vacuum dried at RT.

For the covalent anchorage of the dendrimers onto the external surface of the MSNs (MSN-G3), a similar procedure than the previously reported for SBA-15 type mesoporous silica was employed.¹⁹ Under nitrogen protective atmosphere, to a suspension of 300 mg of surfactant-free MSNs in 150 mL of dry CH_2Cl_2 , the freshly twice-concentrated solution of the silylated dendrimers was added and allowed to stir overnight at RT. Subsequently, MSNs-G3 were thoroughly washed with CH_2Cl_2 , and vacuum dried overnight at RT. HR MAS NMR δ_H (500 MHz; D_2O) 5.34 (br, $NHCONH$), 5.20 (br, $NHCONH$), 3.27 (4H, br, $CH_2NHCONH$), 3.19 (30H, br, CH_2NH_2), 2.84 (84H, br, CH_2N), 2.06 (30H, br, NH_2), 1.92 (58H, br, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 1.78 (4H, br, $CH_2CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 0.85 (2H, t, CH_2Si).

MSN-G3-SS nanomaterial was prepared as follows: to a suspension of 40 mg MSN-G3 in 40 mL of degassed EtOH, Hünig's base (35 μ L, 0.2 mmol) was added under inert atmosphere. Subsequently, CBA (8.7 mg, 0.033 mmol) in EtOH (2 mL) was added to the previous mixture under vigorous stirring. The temperature of the reaction was set to 50 °C, and the system was rapidly stirred and kept under inert atmosphere conditions in darkness. After 3

days of reaction, the mixture was centrifugated and thoroughly washed with EtOH. After vacuum drying at RT, a pale yellow solid was obtained.

2.5 Dye loading and preliminary release experiment

For the dye loading of the MSN-G3-SS material, samples of 5 mg of MSN-G3 were suspended in a 2 M FFA ethanolic solution (5 mL) and allowing to stir overnight at RT, in order to facilitate the diffusion of the dye inside the mesopores. Then, the procedure described for the synthesis of MSN-G3-SS was followed, capping the system with the dye inside. Finally, the dye-loaded nanomaterial was extensively washed with phosphate buffered saline solution (0.01M phosphate, 0.154M NaCl) (PBS 1x) to remove the maximum amount as possible of dye molecules adsorbed within the material surface. The release experiment was performed in a Transwell® Permeable Supports where, dye-loaded MSN-G3-SS suspensions in 0.5 mL of PBS 1x were placed in two different transwell inserts. To one of the samples, a 50 mM DTT solution in PBS 1x (1.5 mL) was added. To the other sample, PBS 1x solution (1.5 mL) with any DTT was added. The transwell plate was then placed into a circular shaking incubator at 37 °C and 80 r.p.m. At different consecutive times, the solution media inside the transwell inserts was removed and replaced by fresh media.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Preparation and characterization of the MSNs family

The bare MSNs were prepared through a sol-gel approach in the presence of a structure-directing agent to obtain an ordered structure of mesopores, by means of a cooperative mechanism.²¹ In order to obtain nanometric sized particles, the modified Stöber method was employed.⁹ Solvent-extracted MSNs were subject to morphological analysis using SEM (Fig. 1), revealing quasi-spherical nanoparticles of around 150 nm diameter.

Fig. 1 SEM image, LA XRD pattern (top left) and hydrodynamic size distribution (bottom left) of the as-prepared MSNs.

Hydrodynamic size of the nanoparticles was assessed by DLS studies, reflecting a slightly bigger diameter due to the water solvation layer. ξ -potential measurement (Table 1) shows a negative-charged surface in agreement with the presence of negative-charged $-SiO^-$ groups of silica in water, though the acid-base equilibrium of deprotonation of the silanol groups:

Measurement	MSN	MSN-G3	MSN-G3-SS
ξ (mV)	-20.2 ± 0.3	$+40 \pm 1$	$+30 \pm 3$
DLS (nm)	190 ± 10	160 ± 20	400 ± 30

Table 1 DLS and ξ -potential measurements of the mesoporous material in aqueous media.

The presence of a ordered hexagonal array of mesopores was confirmed by the LA XRD pattern (Fig. 1, where four reflections [(10), (11), (20) and (21)] procedent from the ordered two-dimensional network of mesopores, with space group $p6mm$, can be observed. In particular, (10) reflection corresponds with the distance between planes containing the center of adjacent mesopores, d_{10} , calculated from Bragg's Law (Table 3). N_2 adsorption/desorption isotherms (Fig. 2) are also in agreement with the presence of the ordered mesoporous structure, exhibiting a typical type IV-isotherm shape,²² which presents a sharp inflection at a relative pressure of *c.a.* 0.35, which indicates the narrow distribution of mesopores with a diameter of 2.7 nm (Table 3).

Fig. 2 N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherm of the mesoporous material.

In order to perform the covalent attachment of the dendrimers to the MSNs surface, dendrimers should be modified in, at least, one of their branches, to introduce a functional group able to react with the silanol rich silica surface. Specifically in this work, one triethoxysilyl group [-Si(OEt)₃] was introduced to one branch per dendrimer in average G3[Si(OEt)₃]₁(NH₂)₁₅, via the formation of an urea bond between a -NH₂ group of the dendrimeric precursor and the isocyanate (-N=C=O) triethoxysilylane derivative. The urea moiety formation and termination of the reaction was verified by means of FTIR spectroscopy. The strong and sharp absorption band at 2272 cm⁻¹, attributed to the vibration of the isocyanate group, disappeared shortly after addition.

The covalent anchorage of the dendrimeric shell to the MSNs was carried out by means of a post-synthesis method. Hydrolysis and condensation reaction between -Si(OEt)₃ groups of the silylated dendrimers and -SiOH silica surface groups was performed. The reaction was carried out under anhydrous conditions in order to avoid the hydrolysis and autocondensation of the silylated dendrimers. The decision to use the third generation of the PPI dendrimers is due to their size, around 2-3 nm, greater than or similar to the size of the mesopores of the MSNs, allowing to a bigger extend an outer surface coating. Furthermore, since a generation dependant cytotoxicity in dendrimers has been reported, the use of this low generation implies a non-toxic approach.²³ The required amount of silylated dendrimers for a complete surface coverage was calculated taking account the textural properties of the MSNs. Specifically, for the MSNs batch employed here, 1 g of MSNs posses 1285 m² of specific surface area, of which approximately a quarter, 321 m², corresponds to the external surface, where the

dendrimeric coating is desired to be anchored. It is estimated that per each nm² of MSNs surface, 4.9 Si-OH are present,²⁴ and supposing that each dendrimer molecule is anchored through three Si-OH groups, 0.39 mmol of the silylated dendrimers are then required. This calculations are made even though complete use of -SiOH surface groups is not expected, taking account, among others, hindering effects within 3G-PPI dendrimers.

DLS measurements indicate a small decrease in the hydrodynamic size of the MSN-G3 material compared to bare MSNs (Table 1). This fact is due to the high positive-charged surface of the functionalized nanoparticles, which avoid agglomeration between nanoparticles through electrostatic repulsions. This high positive-charged surface (Table 1) arises from the protonation equilibrium of the large number of -NH₂ groups, in aqueous media.²⁵

In order to confirm the successful insertion of the dendrimers, TGA and HR MAS studies were performed. The organic content of the MSN-G3 was estimated to be a 20%, which corresponds to the observed loss of mass, in dry basis, in TGA (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 TGA of the mesoporous materials.

Figure 4 shows the ¹H HR MAS NMR spectrum of MSN-G3, which proves that the organic matter present in the MSNs indeed corresponds to the 3G-PPI dendrimer, since the resonances almost match to the counterpart signals in the solution NMR spectrum of the silylated dendrimer.

Fig. 4 ¹H HR MAS NMR spectrum of MSN-G3 in D₂O.

One step ahead, ²⁹Si MAS NMR spectrum was acquired (Fig. 5) to confirm the covalent anchorage of the dendrimeric coating, instead of being just a messy mass physisorbed onto the MSNs surface by, *v.g.* electrostatic interactions. The resonances in the spectrum at around -102 and -112 ppm represent Q³ [Si(OSi)₃(OX)] and Q⁴ [Si(OSi)₄] silicon sites (X = O, C),

respectively. The populations of these silicon environments were calculated using the areas of the Q signals. As alkoxy silane grafting takes place on the MSNs surface there is an 5.90% decrease on the Q³ population together with the corresponding increase in Q⁴ population, which proves that there has been a conversion from Si-OH to fully condensed species. This fact explicitly confirms the existence of covalent linkages between the silica surface and the silylated dendrimers.

Fig. 5 ²⁹Si MAS NMR spectrum of MSN and MSN-G3 and percent populations of Q environments for each sample (inset).

The next step for the fabrication of the redox-responsive MSNs system (MSN-G3-SS) was the cross-linking of the dendrimeric coating, as detailed in the experimental section. The cross-linking reaction was accomplished by means of a *N*-Michael addition between primary amines of the dendrimeric coating and the α - β insaturated carbonyl of the CBA cross-linker. In order to ensure a dense dendrimeric network to afford a complete capping of the mesopores, the amount of CBA employed was optimized to cross-link every -NH₂ group with a neighbouring -NH₂. Taking into account that, in average, only one -NH₂ group per dendrimer was silylated, there were still 15 -NH₂ free groups. Hence, 7.5 equivalents of CBA were added per dendrimer. The amount of dendrimers was estimated from the organic content found in TGA (*ca.* 20 %) which corresponds to the mass of dendrimer per gram of MSN-G3 and, therefore, 0.11 mmol of dendrimers per gram of MSN-G3 were calculated.

For a quickly estimation of the CBA insertion, TGA was carried out (Fig. 3). Unexpectedly, the organic matter found was higher than the total amount organic matter added to the reaction media. This fact could be explained assuming that the solvent, EtOH, would be trapped inside the mesopores and quickly liberated after combustion of the organic coating around 250 °C. EAs were performed for sulfur quantification (Table 2), and *a priori*, it seems that the amount of sulfur is low since, if every -NH₂ group had been cross-linked, it should be around 5%. However, a closer look at the high contents of carbon and hydrogen, probably due to trapped ethanol, glimpses a higher content in sulfur. In addition, using N% of MSN-G3 as reference, which also drops for MSN-G3-SS, supports that a higher amount of sulfur should be present in an ethanol-free MSN-G3-SS sample.

Sample	C	H	N	S	org. mat.
MSN	3.64	1.89	0.02	0.02	4.21
MSN-G3	12.00	4.30	4.60	0.04	20.32
MSN-G3-SS	47.33	8.35	2.46	2.32	68.50

Table 2 EAs and organic matter (org.mat.) percent of the dendrimeric coated mesoporous materials.

Another fact that supported the possible trapping of ethanol inside the mesopores was found when performing ¹H HR MAS studies to a MSN-G3-SS sample, previously degassed under temperature and vacuum, and ethanol resonances clearly predominated in the spectrum.

N₂ sorption measurement of MSN-G3 still exhibits the typical IV-type isotherm, while cross-linked MSN-G3-SS shows an isotherm characteristic of non-porous material (Fig. 2). The change of sorption isotherms, together with a decrease of surface area and pore volume, indicated the capping effect, of the dendrimeric network after cross-linking (Table 3),²⁶ in dried material.²⁷ In this way, the presence of an H4-type of hysteresis²⁸ indicates the narrowing of the mesopores at their entrance. The decrease observed in d₁₀ distance (calculated from LA XRD patterns of calcined samples), specially for MSN-G3-SS, comes from a distortion in the LA XRD pattern which is probably due to the damage of the mesoporous structure after 3 days reaction in hot-ethanolic solution.

DLS and ξ -potential measurements of MSN-G3 and MSN-G3-SS show an increase in the hydrodynamic sizes and a decrease of the positive-charged surfaces, respectively (Table 1). Both fact are anticipated, the first one is due to the cross-linking reaction since, although interdendrimers reaction of the same nanoparticle is favoured, it can also occur between different nanoparticles, therefore agglomerating them. The later is due to the loss of -NH₂ groups when reacting with the cross-linker to be transformed into amides, as expected.

Sample	d ₁₀ (nm)	S _{BET} (m ² /g)	V _P (cm ³ /g)	D _P (nm)
MSN	3.9	1048	1.67	2.8
MSN-G3	3.7	578	0.90	2.7
MSN-G3-SS	3.5	65	0.28	-

Table 3 Structural and textural properties of the mesoporous materials.

Figure 6 shows a TEM image of MSN-G3-SS material after staining with 1% phosphotungstic acid (PTA) to reveal the organic material, where it can be clearly noticed the cross-linked dendrimeric coating and the mesostructure.

Fig. 6 TEM image of MSN-G3-SS after staining with 1% PTA.

3.2 Preliminary release test

The fluorescent dye molecule FFA was chosen to assess the redox-responsive behaviour of MSN-G3-SS material. Dendrimers are no static structures in solution, so a slow diffusion of FAA through the aliphatic branches of dendrimers in control experiment was anticipated, as well as some FAA was expected to be adsorbed in the dendrimeric coating and subsequently to diffuse.^{29,30} The release test (Fig. 7) showed how the addition of DTT has a burst

effect in the release of the cargo compared to the slow diffusion from the control sample. For further assessment of the release behaviour of the redox-responsive system and the specificity of the CBA cross-linker, HBA cross-linker was employed instead, showing non-induced release with the addition of DTT.

Fig. 7 Time evolution of FFA release from MSN-G3-SS in the absence and presence of DTT.

4 Conclusions

A novel redox-responsive system for smart drug delivery purposes has been unveiled in this project, which to the best of our knowledge is the first one based on MSNs with a cross-linked dendrimeric covalent coating as capping agent.

MSNs were synthesized, surfactant-extracted and functionalized with 3G-PPI dendrimers to finally form a dendrimeric network after cross-linking with CBA disulfide molecule. TGA and EA showed the increase in organic matter due to the cross-linked dendrimeric coating. In addition, trapping of ethanol inside mesopores during synthesis, was confirmed by HR MAS studies. Nitrogen sorption isotherms were acquired, showing the enclosing of the mesopores. DLS measurements show aggregation of the nanoparticles to some extent during the cross-linking reaction. Also, damage of the mesoporous structure, due to the time and temperature conditions of the cross-linking reaction, was found after LA XRD studies. Finally, redox-responsive release of a FFA dye as model molecule was confirmed, exhibiting a burst effect in the release of the dye due to the disulfide cleavage because of the DTT action compared with the control sample or even with HBA cross-linked material.

5 Further work

Promising results obtained in this research work, encourage us to continue working on this redox-responsive drug delivery system. The synthetic route of the MSN-G3-SS should be enhanced by employing a high "cell-friendly" solvent, ideally water, which will require the use of a water-soluble cross-linker. On top to a high water soluble cross-linker, the best choice should also present a better reactivity with amines, in order to employ less aggressive conditions for mesoporous material. A candidate with these requirements is commercially available, the water-soluble form of the Lomant's reagent, 3,3'-dithiobis[sulfosuccinimidylpropionate], only having the drawback of producing side-products, which entails further purification of the MSN-G3-SS, not necessary when employing CBA since side-products are not generated.

Another disadvantage which should be overcome is the aggregation between nanoparticles. This can be achieved by adding large polymeric molecules, namely polyethylen glycol (PEG), to

the dendrimeric coating before cross-linking. The use of PEG will also provide the system with stealth properties, which is required if the system is expected to use in biomedical applications.

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